

Defluoridation of water with iron-rust

Anamika Srivastava^{*a}, Minaxi Lohani^a, Sanjib Kumar Kar^b and Devi Dutt Upreti^b

^aDepartment of Chemistry, Integral University, Kursi Road, Lucknow-226 020, Uttar Pradesh, India

E-mail : anamikasrivastav2006@gmail.com

^bGeological Survey of India, Sector-E, Aliganj, Lucknow-226 020, Uttar Pradesh, India

E-mail : sk.kar54@gmail.com

Manuscript received 08 September 2016, revised 20 February 2017, accepted 28 February 2017

Abstract : Iron-rust can be used as defluoridating agent. Rust retains fluoride involving various physical, chemical or ion exchange mechanism. Maximum removal of fluoride ion from fluorinated water by 2.0 g of washed dried and sieved rust is 4900–5000 µg of fluoride in seven days (168 h). Rust is disinfected by heating at 180 °C. Mineral goethite FeO.OH formed by hydrolysis of rust acts as a defluoridating agent is proved with the study of X-ray diffraction (XRD) of rust (Blank) and rust containing co-precipitated fluoride. Exchange of OH⁻ ion with F⁻ ion occurs at the surface of the rust.

Keywords : Co-precipitation, defluoridation, fluoride, goethite.

Introduction

The land water ecosystem developed in response to geological, geochemical and hydrodynamic process varies from place to place. It leads to different level of concentration of essential and trace elements¹⁻⁵. Area of excess or different level of concentration of essential and trace elements observed in human and plant kingdom. Very few systematic studies have so far been carried out to establish geological-geochemical linkage with concentration/accumulation of elements. Aswathanarayana⁶ proposed a geochemical model to account for the high fluoride content in surface and ground water of northern Tanzania. Access to adequate safe drinking water is a great challenge for rural communities in India^{5,7,8}. Kar and Prasad⁹ in its study of geogenic disease and its relation to the geochemical environment in the Ghazipur district of Uttar Pradesh, India, brought out geochemical correlation of soil water interactions with prevalent disease. Fluoride is a vital micronutrient for human physiological development and growth. It reduces incidence of dental carries and delays or reverses the progression of incipient lesions. The principal public health measures taken to prevent dental carries are water defluoridation. In India defluoridation measures are attempted since 1986. Three pronged strategy comprising (a) provision of fluoride-free alternative source through pipe water, (b) defluoridation technique, (c) preventive measures, were adopted.

Defluoridation of water can be performed with the use of activated alumina filters, synthetic ion exchangers, reverse osmosis or precipitation process^{10,11}. Excess intake of fluoride can lead to both visible and non-visible debilitating diseases. The visible symptoms include dental and skeletal fluorosis. Non visible disease includes kidney and lung disorders, brittle skeletal system etc.¹². Endemic fluorosis known as genu-valgum is common in parts of Andhra Pradesh and Tamilnadu¹³. Even today fluorosis persists as disease without proper treatment. Taking precautionary early measures is the only effective way for prevention of fluorosis. Change or modification of water supply is the only long term practical solution. The paper presents the finding of fluoride removal capability of iron-rust. It can be used for treatment of water at the point of use, at the house hold level at low-cost benefit.

Results and discussion

Iron oxide containing laterite, goethite, magnetite and haematite had been used for removal of arsenic from the drinking water¹⁴. The study suggests that iron oxide minerals have low solubility in water and contributes iron on dissolving. This dissolved iron helps in the adsorption of arsenic present either in the form of arsenite (AsO₃³⁻) or arsenate (AsO₄³⁻) ion and in co-precipitation. In the present paper we have used rust (mixture of iron oxide) for the removal of fluoride from drinking water. The removal of

fluoride from drinking water requires an understanding of various physical and chemical interactions between fluoride and oxide minerals. Chemically rust when dissolved in water forms iron and mineral goethite by hydrolysis and releasing H^+ ion which decreases the pH of the solution¹⁴. In the present case also pH is found to be 3.6 when 2.5 g of the rust is dissolved in distilled water (Table 1C). Since because of nearly same ionic radius [OH^- ion = 1.40 Å, F^- ion = 1.33 Å]¹⁵, OH^- ion of mineral goethite are replaced by F^- ion forming iron fluoride. The iron fluoride gets co-precipitated with the oxides of iron. Formation of mineral goethite and iron fluoride hydrate was confirmed by X-ray diffraction analysis (XRD) when both rust blank treated with distilled water only and rust containing co-precipitated fluoride was analyzed by XRD (Fig. 1 and Fig. 2). Rust blank shows the presence of mineral goethite $FeO.OH$ (Fig. 1)¹⁶. The exchange of OH^- ion with F^- ion is further supported by the observation that increase in pH on increasing the mass of rust is observed when fluoride solution is treated with rust. It is because more mass of the rust will form more quantity of mineral goethite, thereby more number of OH^- ion are produced by exchange of fluoride ion. These OH^- ion will remove comparatively more number of H^+ ion thereby increasing

pH. Further the pH of the fluoride solution decreases to a lesser extent (4.2–4.5) as compared to distilled water (3.6) when both solution are treated with same mass of rust, it is also because of more neutralization of H^+ ion of fluoride solution with OH^- ion of mineral goethite. Because of the highest reactivity of the fluoride ion, presence of other ions like Cl^- or SO_4^{2-} etc. will not affect the formation of iron fluoride hydrate and thus will not affect the removal of fluoride ion from drinking water. Tap water used here (Fig. 3c) was containing Cl^- and SO_4^{2-} 12 ppm and < 2.0 ppm respectively. The results had already been published¹⁷.

Different concentration of fluoride were taken and treated with the same quantity of rust. The solution is kept for seven days with occasional shaking. After seven days it is dry filtered and concentration of non co-precipitated fluoride is determined with ion selective fluoride electrode. The results in Table 1A suggest that maximum concentration of fluoride that can be removed by 2.0 g of rust in seven days is 4900–5000 micrograms. Further results in (Figs. 3a and 3b) suggest that co-precipitation process is completed within seven days or 168 h.

Fig. 3c shows that co-precipitation of fluoride with rust is also observed when fluoride/water solution is taken in bulk. Table 1B presents the concentration of fluoride

Fig. 1. Diffractogram of rust blank.

Fig. 3. Bar diagram of fluoride removal.

the added reagents and titrate the cooked solution with 5 M sodium hydroxide slowly with stirring using pH meter until pH of the solution comes within 5.0 to 5.5. Cool the solution to room temperature. Dilute to one litre and finally store in a polyethylene bottle. Standard fluoride

solution (100 ppm) is prepared by dissolving 0.221 g NaF in a litre of DM water. Prepare 0.1, 1.0, 5.0 and 10 ppm fluoride standard solution by serial dilution of stock 100 ppm fluoride solution with DM water. Store all standard solution in polyethylene bottle.

Table 1. Removal of fluoride by different mass of iron rust

Sr. No.	Quantity of rust taken in g (80-mesh)	Concentration/volume of 100 ppm fluoride solution taken ($\mu\text{g/ml}$)	Concentration of fluoride left after co-precipitation (μg) Reading observed \times volume of fluoride solution taken	Concentration of fluoride (μg)	
				Removed by the rust	Found on analysis of rust containing co-precipitated fluoride
(A) Removal of maximum concentration of fluoride by 2.0 g of rust (168 h)					
1.	2.0	2000/10	10	990	–
2.	2.0	2000/20	58	1942	–
3.	2.0	3000/30	47	2953	–
4.	2.0	4000/40	249	3751	–
5.	2.0	5000/50	440	4560	–
6.	2.0	6000/60	1506	4494	–
7.	2.0	7000/70	2049	4951 (70 ppm)	–
8.	2.0	8000/80	3080	4920	–
9.	2.0	9000/90	4077	4923	–
10.	2.0	10000/100	5010	4990	–
(B) Results of co-precipitated fluoride on the rust in 72 h					
1.	0.5	7000/70	5817	1183	982
2.	1.0	7000/70	4794	2206	2150
3.	1.5	7000/70	3850	3150	3010
4.	2.0	7000/70	2900	4100	3690
5.	2.5	7000/70	1837	5163	4968
(C) Co-precipitation of fluoride ion by different quantities of rust in seven days (168 h)					
					pH of solution after treatment with rust
1.	0.5	7000/70	5900	1100	4.2
2.	1.0	7000/70	4754	2246	4.4
3.	1.5	7000/70	3494	3506	4.4
4.	2.0	7000/70	2274	4726 (68 ppm)	4.5
5.	2.5	7000/70	1358	5642	4.5
6.	2.5	Distilled water/70	–	–	3.6
7.	–	7000/70	–	–	6.4
8.	–	Distilled water	–	–	7.0

Instrumentation :

Thermoscientific Orion Dual star pH/ion-selective electrode meter is used to measure the pH as well as fluoride concentration in solution. X-Ray diffractometer (XRD) of PAN alytical X'pert pro model is used to get diffractogram of the sample. Working voltage is kept at 45 KV/40 mA and copper metal is used for generating K- α lines of X-ray.

Procedure :

Rust is collected washed with water and distilled wa-

ter several times and disinfected by heating at 180 °C in an oven. Dried rust is crushed, pulverized and sieved. Fluoride solution of different concentration (1000–10000 micrograms) are taken in polyethylene bottle of 100 ml capacity of TORSON made. Different quantities of rust (0.5, 1.0, 1.5, 2.0 and 2.5 g) are added in each bottle and capped tightly. The solution is kept for different hours of time e.g. 1, 2, 3, 4, 5, 6, 7, 8, 16, 24, 48, 72, 96, 120, 144, 168 and 192 h with occasional shaking. Room temperature was 27–28 °C. After certain time the solution

Table 2. Statistical test for time and rust removal for significance

Significance level : 0.05

Descriptive statistics :

Sample	Frequency	Mean	Variance	Standard deviation	Standard error	Minimum	First quartile	Median	Third quartile	Maximum
24	7	120	2688	51.846	19.596	48	72	120	168	192
3332	7	4510	138765	372.512	140.796	4046	4067	4538	4920	4950

Student's t test for independent samples/two-tailed test :

The test is computed under the assumption that the two theoretical variances are equal

Confidence interval at 95.00% of the difference of the means : -4699.726 to -4080.274

t (observed value) -30.882

t (critical value) 2.179

DF 12

Two-tailed p-value < 0.0001

Alpha 0.05

Conclusion :

At the level of significance Alpha=0.050 the decision is to reject the null hypothesis of equality of the means

In other words, the difference between the means is significant

Student's t test for independent samples/two-tailed test :

The test is computed under the assumption that the two theoretical variances are not equal (Satterthwaite's method)

Confidence interval at 95.00% of the difference of the means : -4734.837 to -4045.163

t (observed value) -30.882

t (critical value) 2.426

DF 6

Two-tailed p-value < 0.0001

Alpha 0.05

Conclusion :

At the level of significance Alpha=0.050 the decision is to reject the null hypothesis of equality of the means

In other words, the difference between the means is significant

Student's t test for independent samples/two-tailed test :

The test is computed under the assumption that the two theoretical variances are not equal (Cochran-Cox's method)

t (observed value) -30.882

t (critical value) 2.448

DF 6

Two-tailed p-value < 0.0001

Alpha 0.05

Conclusion :

At the level of significance Alpha = 0.050 the decision is to reject the null hypothesis of equality of the means

In other words, the difference between the means is significant

Synthesis table for Student's test :

Variance s	Observed t	Method	DF	Critical t	Pr > t
Unequal	-30.882	Satterthwaite	6.232	2.426	< 0.0001
	-30.882	Cochran-Cox	6	2.448	< 0.0001
Equal	-30.882		12	2.179	< 0.0001

was dry filtered. Filtrate is kept for fluoride measurement. Residue is washed several times with distilled wa-

ter, dried and kept for analysis of co-precipitated fluoride. Thus the estimation of fluoride can be divided into

Fig. 4. Correlation and determinant of significant (R^2) graph of removal of rust with increasing time.

two parts.

Analysis of non co-precipitated fluoride in solution :

After dry filtration, 10 ml solution is taken in polyethylene beaker of 50 ml capacity, 10 ml of TISAB is added. pH of solution is maintained between 5.0 to 5.5 with pH electrode by acid/base addition and fluoride concentration is measured with ion-selective electrode.

Analysis of rust containing co-precipitated fluoride :

Different mass (0.5, 1.0, 1.5, 2.0 and 2.5 g) of rust were added in 70 ml of 100 ppm fluoride solution (7000 g of fluoride ion) and kept for three days (72 h). After three days it is filtered, washed with DM water several times and dried at room temperature. 0.25 g from each sample of rust was fused with 2.0 g fusion mixture (Na_2CO_3 : NaNO_3) at 200, 400 and 600 °C each for one hour in muffle furnace. Fused mass in nickel crucible is dissolved in 20 ml water, added 20 ml citrate buffer, make up to 100 ml and kept it over night. Taken 10 ml solution, added 10 ml TISAB and measured fluoride concentration.

References

1. Y. Bachmat, "Groundwater as a Part of Water System", in : 'Groundwater contamination and control', ed. V. Zoller, Marcel Dekker, Inc., New York, 1994.
2. V. Mani, H. Kaur and M. Mohini, *J. Ind. Poll. Cont.*, 2005, **21**, 101.
3. Gomez-Serrano, A. Garcia-Macius, A. Espinosa-Mansilla and Valenzuela-Calahorro, *Wat. Res.*, 1998, **32**, 1.
4. K. V. Sastry and P. Rathee. *J. Natcon.*, 1999, **11**, 175.
5. J. R. Pffafliin and E. N. Zeigler, "Encyclopedia of Environmental Science and Engineering", Taylor and Francis, 2006.
6. U. Aswathanarayana, P. Lahermo, E. Malisa and J. T. Nanyaro, *Env. Geochem. & Health*, 1985, 243.
7. T. Girma, "Extent and Significant Use of Low Quality Water in Agriculture", 2005.
8. V. P. Kudesia, "Water Pollution", Pragati Prakashan, Meerut, 1992.
9. S. K. Kar and S. Prasad, *Int. Med. Geol. Asso. News Lett.*, 2007, **11**, 10.
10. J. Fawell, K. Bailay, J. Chilton, E. Dahi, L. Fewtrell and Y. Magara, "Fluoride in Drinking Water", WHO, IWA Publishing, 2006.
11. L. Feenstra, L. Vasak and J. Griffioen, "Fluoride in Ground Water : Overview and Evaluation of Removal methods", IGRAC, 2007.
12. P. E. John De Zuane, "Handbook of Drinking Water Quality", Wiley India Pvt. Ltd., 2013.
13. C. B. Dissanayake and R. Chandrajith, "Introduction to Medical Geology", Springer-Verlag, 2009.
14. Sonia Aredes, Bern Klein and Marek Pawlik, *J. Clean. Prod.*, 2012, **29-30**, 208.
15. A. Srivastava, M. Lohani, S. K. Kar and D. D. Upreti, *Int. J. Env. Research and Dev.*, 2015, **5**, 7.
16. "Mineral Powder diffraction file search manual", Published by Joint Committee on Powdered diffraction standard (JCPDS), International Centre for diffraction Data, USA, 1980.
17. A. Srivastava, M. Lohani, S. K. Kar and D. D. Upreti, *Int. J. Geom. & Geosc.*, 2015, **6**, 1450.

